

Methods of Teaching Russian to Students Majoring in Non-Foreign Language

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Abstract: With the development of our society, there is a huge impact on the content of foreign language teaching. The quality and quantity of information needed by students is inevitably increasing. Russian no longer seen as a separate science, but as a necessary element in a complex and multi-level educational structure. More and more often, the question arises about the need to develop students' professional mobility, i.e. the possibility and ability to successfully switch to another activity or change the type of work.

Currently, there are many methods for students to learn a foreign language in higher education institutions. Each of the methods has certain features, for example, some are more popular and in demand, while others are less popular. This work is devoted to the review of methods for students to learn Russian. Let us consider each of them in detail.

Keywords: method, communication, modern world, Russian, students and teachers, foreign language teaching, learning process.

The digitalization and informatization of the modern world have significantly affected, among other things, the availability and volume of information, its diversity and, at the same time, its contradiction. The change in the pace of life associated with these processes, inevitably affects the main cognitive functions of the person: attention, thinking, memory. It seems impossible to modernize the modern educational system so that it can meet the new challenges, without taking into account the processes occurring both in the public sphere, and on the personal level. At present, it recognized that the competency-based approach currently recognized as a means of building a productive system that meets new demands on a functional level.

The competence approach strengthens the practical component; the priority becomes the development of personal qualities and value orientations of students. Consequently, it is necessary to expand the set of methods and technologies aimed at solving new problems, which should contribute to the integration of the above-mentioned significant elements.

Awareness of the importance of modern methods stimulates the search for new technologies of their development in teaching a foreign language to non-native speakers. This desire has led us to consider the possibility of using and considering different methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language.

Now we will look at the direct method technique. The essence of the method is that the teacher pays more attention to the study of the spoken language itself, which used in everyday life. The developers of this method agreed that the intermediary language, that is, the language in which teaching conducted, inhibits the learning of a foreign language. Thus, students artificially

introduced to the world of the language they are learning. The class taught in Russian, explanations and the teacher in Russian must give new topics. Here we observe the use of only Russian-language literature. In learning Russian through this method, the role of the teacher in the successful assimilation of knowledge by students is key, that is, his speech must be absolutely clear and correct, and the pronunciation must be perfect, as students will be constantly repeating just after the teacher. For the direct method of training as a teacher is best suited to a native Russian speaker.

Considering the following method, we can say that the grammar-translation method is the main one in the modern education system. A classic method used for decades. We can also explain its prevalence by the fact that most of the teachers themselves taught using this method.

The goal of the grammar-translation method is to be able to read and translate with the help of grammatical rules.

It should be noted that this method has certain disadvantages. First, it pays insufficient attention to the lexical part. In other words, the study of vocabulary reduced to a mechanical memorization of words. Secondly, reading and translation are done in a strict form. In addition, the texts offered for reading usually refer to complex fiction; hence, the student learns only literary language. In addition, from this we can conclude that it will be very difficult for a student caught up in a language environment to understand those around him, even with a good knowledge of literary language. Next, we will consider the audiolingual method, the creators of which the American linguist C. Freeze are and the methodologist R. Lado. Their concept has had a significant impact on learning.

As for learning, the scientists put forward the following is a comprehensive mastery of a foreign language, that is, all kinds of oral and written communication. Learning a foreign language inextricably linked to penetration into the culture of its people. Professor P. Gubernia argues that anyone learning a foreign language, like the naturally deaf, is truly deaf to some sounds of the foreign language and, in particular, to those that are not in the phonetic system of his native language. He believes that the foreign language learner must first; develop new skills.

The authors of this method believed that learning a foreign language carried out in the form of live communication, so an important factor in the pedagogical process was to create conditions for the imitation of a real communicative situation, so that learning would proceed in an atmosphere of natural speech, stimulating the assimilation of sounds, rhythm of speech.

Based on the above, we can determine that the essence of both methods is the transmission of language through clear structures, and as for memorization, it occurs with the help of audio and video recordings. Both methods built on induction, when learning goes from rule to example, it noted that for university students who are not specialized in learning languages, audiolingual and audiovisual methods are suitable only if they are used in conjunction with other training programs.

The most common method, as our research has shown, is the method of the communicative approach, focused on the practice of communication. This technique “works” perfectly in Russia and in the CIS (Commonwealth of Independent States).

The communicative method implies a great activity of students, as well as the creation of real communication situations. The teacher’s task comes down to involving everyone in the audience in the conversation. When recreating a dialogue, the student has an opportunity to apply in practice all the knowledge he or she has acquired. In our opinion, a very important advantage of the communicative method is that it has a huge variety of exercises: it uses role-plays, dialogues, simulation of real communication.

Now in our modern world new methods of teaching Russian are being created, which are often based on the experience of subject and language integrated learning Content and Language Integrated Learning. It allows students to form linguistic and communicative competences in a non-native language in the same learning context in which they form and develop general academic knowledge and skills. This method opens the door to attract a large audience of foreign language

learners, builds the confidence of young people in their abilities, and gives support to those who have not been successful enough in learning languages in the traditional form.

Content and Language Integrated Learning provides for a number of subjects, which are basic for students, to be taught in the language of international communication. Thus, the student is strongly motivated to learn a foreign language not only as a means of communication, but also as a necessary tool in mastering the future profession. Moreover, many educational institutions practice the use of Russian at international conferences held within their walls, which necessitates a high level of language proficiency not only for students, but also for teachers.

However, unfortunately, at this stage there are some problems in the implementation of Content and Language Integrated Learning in the educational process. On the one hand, foreign language teachers, as a rule, do not have the necessary amount of knowledge to teach a particular subject, i.e. special education. On the other hand, the level of foreign language skills of subject teachers, as a rule, is not too high. That is why today, as never before, educational institutions need highly qualified specialists who are able to give lectures and conduct practical classes in two languages.

One of the main methods in teaching a foreign language is the use of computer technology: Internet sites, blogs, Skype, e-mail and other resources.

It should be noted that more than 50% of the total number of hours are now devoted to students' independent work. Properly dosed distribution and use of Internet resources is definitely a necessary element of training, and the teacher, in this case, acts as an assistant, whose main task is to direct Internet addiction of students in the necessary direction. One of the ways of language immersion and overcoming the language barrier is communication with native speakers online, for example, via Skype. Communication with peer students is one of the ways to practice listening comprehension.

The use of e-mail and blogs should be noted in the learning process. Electronic correspondence compared to paper correspondence has a number of advantages: it is more convenient, faster, carried out from any audience and at any level of language proficiency and promotes the establishment of friendships.

Despite the advantages listed above, the Internet can definitely never become an alternative to textbooks. Internet resources are only one of the tools to help learn the material in the classroom, the main role of which undoubtedly belongs to the teacher.

Therefore, to summarize, we can say that all methods have a number of distinctive features. As human experience shows, most of them have been developed because of integration of traditional and modern methods of teaching. The multilevel approach allows the development of an individual human personality, affects his worldview, system of values, self-identification, ability to think. All methods without exception are aimed at the development of four language skills: reading, writing, speaking and listening. Much emphasis placed on the use of audio, video, and interactive resources. Thanks to the variety of methods, every student and teacher can choose a methodology that will help them achieve their goals.

References

1. Кенжабоев, А. Э. & Кенжабоев, Ж. А. (2017). Умумтаълим мактаблари ўқитувчиларида касбий компетентликни шакллантиришнинг илмий-педагогик асослари. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (11), 22-26.
2. Кенжабоев, Ж. А. & Кучкинов, Х. Х. (2017). САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНАЯ РАБОТА УЧАЩИХСЯ НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА. *Вопросы педагогики*, (9), 33-35.
3. Kenjabayev, J. A. Linguistic features of the development of oral speech competence of students of the direction of physical culture education (on the example of sports terminology). *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences.-UK*, 11, 48-51.

4. Соляхова, Л. Р. (2021). Использование Инновационных Методов При Развитии Потенциала Обучению Английского Языка У Курсантов Академии Вооруженных Сил Республики Узбекистан. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(11), 1166-1171.
5. Кенжабаев, Ж. (2022). The implementation of literature in teaching speaking for advanced students. *Общество и инновации*, 3(2/S), 262-265.
6. Кенжабаев, Ж. (2023). СОВРЕМЕННЫЙ ЭТАП РАЗВИТИЯ НАУКИ О ЯЗЫКЕ. *Экономика и социум*, (2 (105)), 704-707.
7. Кенжабоев, А, & Кенжабоев, Ж. (2015). Тарбия технологияси ва унинг долзарблиги. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (4), 61-64.
8. Кенжабоев, А. Э., & Кенжабоев, Ж. А. (2016). ХОРИЖИЙ ТИЛЛАРНИ ЎРГАТИШДА ПЕДАГОГИК ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАР. *Ученый XXI века*, (3-2 (16)), 44-49.
9. Кенжабоев, Ж. А. (2017). Психолого-педагогические аспекты формирования диалога как компонента иноязычного обучения. *Вестник современной науки*, (3-2), 48-50.
10. Nigora, S. (2021). On The Manuscript Copies Of “Al Kashshof” By Makhmud Zamakhshari. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, 12(7), 2032-2042.
11. Sulaymonova, N. A. (2020). The Work “Al-Mufasssal Fi San’ati-L-I’rob” By Mahmud Zamakhshari and Its Lithography Copies. *The American Journal of Applied sciences*, 2(09), 17-24.
12. Sulaymonova, N., & Sulaymonova, K. (2015). A GREAT SCIENTIST OF KHOREZM. *International Journal*, (1).
13. Сулаймонова, Н. & Сулаймонова, К. (2015). Фразеологизмы в произведении Махмуда Замахшари «асо-л-балого». *Восточный факел*, 1(1), 21-24.
14. Sulaymanova, N. (2019). Confidential Review at Literary Heritage Of Mahmud Zamakhshariy. *European Journal Of Humanities And Social Sciences*, (6), 162-166.
15. SULAYMONOVA, N., & SULAYMANOVA, K. ZAMAKHSHARIY” S SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITY. *MATER I ALLARI*, 491.
16. Toxirovna, K. F. (2021). LIFELONG LEARNING–LLL–THE BASIS OF PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(8), 119-123.
17. Tohirova, K. F. (2021, February). Bologna Treaty and ECTS (EUROPEAN CREDIT TRANSFER SYSTEM). In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 14, No. 1, pp. 25-31).
18. Хусаинова, Ф. Т. (2020). ТАШКЕНТ В ПРОШЛОМ–В ЦЕННОМ ПИСЬМЕННОМ НАСЛЕДИИ «ТАРИХИ ЖАДИДАЙИ ТОШКАНД». *Review of law sciences*, (1), 183-187.
19. Khusainova, F. (2020). Ancestral heritage is a priceless treasure. Human and its spiritual problems in Avesto. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (I (2)), 135-137.
20. Yashnarovna, A. A. M. (2021, November). Intelligent Management Model Of Business Processes Of Production With The Use Of Fuzzy Logic Apparatus. In *2021 International Conference on Information Science and Communications Technologies (ICISCT)* (pp. 1-3). IEEE.
21. Abdul-Azalova, M. Y., & Mamatova, N. M. (2021). Big data technologies in technological and business processes automatization. *Big Data and Advanced Analytics*, (7-1), 50-58.
22. Muhamediyeva, D., & Abdul-Azalova, M. (2022). Application of the theory of fuzzy logic for analysis of management systems of business processes of an enterprise. *Scientific Collection «InterConf+»*, (22 (113)), 467-471.

23. Mengliyev, B. (2022). PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE OF A MODERN PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHER. *Science and innovation*, 1(B7), 554-556.
24. Sagdullayevna, K. V. (2022). Yosh Gimnastikachilarning Maxsus Tayyorgarlik Bosqichidagi Faoliyatining Mazmuni Va Uslubiyati. *International Journal Of Philosophical Studies And Social Sciences*, 110-113.
25. Менглиев, Б. Н., & Умиров, Ш. Б. (2020). Теоретические Основы Внедрения Педагогических Технологий На Занятиях Физической Культурой. In *Инновационное Развитие: Потенциал Науки И Современного Образования* (Рр. 119-121).
26. Ixtiyorovich, N. N., & Abdurashidovich, U. A. (2022). Study the Location of the Useful Component from the Tailings of the Gold Recovery Plant. *International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology*, 2(1), 5-8.
27. Khayitov, O. G. O., Ziyodov, N. R., Fatkhiddinov, A. O. T. O., & Umirzoqov, A. A. (2021). THE INTENSITY OF THE EFFECT OF THE EXPLOSION OF BOREHOLE CHARGES OF EXPLOSIVES IN MULTI-STRENGTH ROCKS OF DEEP QUARRIES. *Scientific progress*, 2(1), 625-630.
28. Бабаев, З. Н. Умирзоков, А. А. & Петросов, Ю. Э. (2020). Техничко-экономическое обоснование кондиций для подсчета запасов горючих сланцев месторождения сангрунтау. *Студенческий вестник*, (10-2), 18-20.
29. Хайитов, О. Джураев, С. Умирзоков, А. Бекманов, Н. & Искандаров, Ж. (2021). НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ РЕЗУЛЬТАТОВ ВСКРЫТИЯ, ИСПЫТАНИЯ И ОСВОЕНИЯ ПОИСКОВО-РАЗВЕДОЧНЫХ СКВАЖИН. *Збірник наукових праць SCIENTIA*.
30. Nasirov, U., Umirzoqov, A., & Fathiddinov, A. (2021). ANALYSIS OF THE MODERN DEVELOPMENT OF MINING AND PROCESSING COMPLEXES IN UZBEKISTAN. *Збірник наукових праць ЛОГОΣ*.
31. Ochilov, S. H. (2017). A., Umirzoqov AA, Determining the optimal distance between parallel-converged borehole charges when blasting high ledges. *Bulletin TSTU–Tashkent*, 3, 167-174.
32. Usmanovich, S. A., Ikhtiyorovich, N. N., & Abdurashidovich, U. A. (2022). Processing of Layout Tails of Gold-Extracting Plants. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 3(1), 7-13.
33. Петросов, Ю., Хайитов, О., Умирзоков, А., Исаманов, У., & Имамбердиев, Ў. (2021). ПРОБЛЕМЫ ДОБЫЧИ И ПЕРЕРАБОТКИ ПОЛЕЗНЫХ ИСКОПАЕМЫХ В УСЛОВИЯХ ГЛУБОКИХ КАРЬЕРОВ. *Збірник наукових праць SCIENTIA*.
34. Samadov, A. U., Nosirov, N. I., & Umirzoqov, A. A. (2022). Overview of the concepts of gold recovery from stale tailings of a gold recovery plant. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMiy JURNALI*, 2(1), 3-8.
35. Umirzoqov, A. (2020). The Tasks of Optimal Design and Research of Systems for Cleaning Gas Emissions of Industrial Enterprises. *International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS) ISSN*.
36. G'ofurovich, K. O., & Abdurashidovich, U. A. (2021). Justification of rational parameters of transshipment points from automobile conveyor to railway transport. *World Economics and Finance Bulletin*, 1(1), 20-25.